

Organization Name: Frictionless Data

Description: Frictionless Data is an open source project within the Open Knowledge Foundation

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Past Experience + Background:

The Frictionless Data team has been collaborating with researchers for the past 6 years on a mission to make research data more open and reproducible. This initiative is an open research data infrastructure project, consisting of a suite of open source software, tooling, specifications, and best practices for data management. We aim to reduce the “frictions” in data that make it difficult to use, publish, and share data, such as when data is in a difficult to use format, is hard to find, or is poorly structured. These collaborations have focused on helping researchers manage their data and promote open science best practices by implementing the Frictionless tooling and data specifications.

As part of the Frictionless Data for Reproducible Research project, we have run 5 large-scale Pilot collaborations (<https://frictionlessdata.io/adoption/#pilot-collaborations>), 9 mini-grant development projects (<https://frictionlessdata.io/adoption/#tool-fund-grantee-projects>), and trained 14 early-career researchers to become open science champions as part of our Fellows programme (<https://fellows.frictionlessdata.io/>). Pilot collaboration projects’ goals span from helping researchers create better data, to cleaning publicly available climate data, to publishing open data in more usable formats. With the mini-grants, grantees have used the Frictionless code to create new open source tools for tasks like publishing open data, editing data schemas, describing field-specific data, and visualizing open research data. Now in the third cohort, the Fellows programme has trained early-career researchers from around the world in data management and open science best practices by using the Frictionless tools and community.

In the Earth sciences domain, we have collaborated with the Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO), Arctic expedition researchers, and several agricultural researchers (in the UK and Kenya).

Topic Area: Component Technologies

Frictionless Data is an open source project that aims to make scientific data more understandable, open, and reproducible. Frictionless consists of a suite of open software, tools, and data standards. The main Python code, Frictionless Framework, allows data users to easily describe their data with metadata and schemas, validate the content and structure of their data, and write reproducible data transformation pipelines that can be understood by humans and machines. Here, we share a short explanation of why Frictionless tooling can help the mission science data processing and two examples of relevant collaborations.

We think this software will benefit the mission science data processing in several ways. First, Frictionless automatically infers metadata and schemas from a data file, and allows users to edit that information. Creating good metadata is vital for downstream data users – if you can't understand the data, you can't use it (or can't *easily* use it). Similarly, having a data schema is useful for interoperability, promoting the usefulness of datasets. The second Frictionless function we think will be helpful is data validation. Frictionless validates both the structure and content of a dataset, using built-in and custom checks. For instance, Frictionless will check for missing values, incorrect data types, or other constraints (e.g. temperature data points that exceed a certain threshold). If any errors are detected, Frictionless will generate a report for the user detailing the error so the user can fix the data during processing. Finally, users can write reproducible data transformation pipelines with Frictionless. Writing declarative transform pipelines allows humans and machines to understand the data cleaning steps and repeat those processes if needed in the future. Collectively, these functions create well documented, high quality, clean data that can then be used in further downstream analysis.

Use Case 1: The Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO) cleans and hosts a wide variety of open oceanography data sets for use by researchers. A main problem for them was data being submitted to them was messy and not standardized, and it was time consuming and difficult for their data managers to clean in a reproducible, documented way. They implemented Frictionless code to create a new data transformation pipeline that ingests the messy data, performs defined cleaning/transforming steps, documents those steps, and produces a cleaned, standardized dataset. It also produces a (human and machine-readable) document detailing all the transformation steps so that downstream users could understand what happened to the data and undo/repeat if necessary. This process not only helps data managers clean data faster and more efficiently, it also drives open science by making the hosted data more understandable and usable while preserving provenance.

Use Case 2: Dryad is a biological data repository with a large user base. In our collaboration, their main issue was that they do not have the people-power to curate all the submitted datasets, so they implemented Frictionless tooling to help data submitters curate their data as they submit it. When data is submitted on the Dryad platform, Frictionless performs validation checks, and generates a report if any errors are found. The data submitter can then fix that error (e.g. there are no headers in row 1) and resubmit. Creating easy-to-understand error reports helps submitters understand how to create more useable, standardized data, and also frees up valuable time for the Dryad data management team. Ultimately, now the Dryad data repository hosts higher quality open science data.

Links

- Fowler, D., et al. Frictionless Data: Making Research Data Quality Visible, International Journal Of Digital Curation. May 2018.
<https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v12i2.577>.
- Daniella Lowenberg and Lilly Winfree. Frictionless Data and Dryad join forces to validate research data. Blog. August 2021.
<https://frictionlessdata.io/blog/2021/08/09/dryad-pilot/>
- Shepherd, A., et al. Frictionless Data Pipelines for Ocean Science. Blog. February 2020.
<https://frictionlessdata.io/blog/2020/02/10/frictionless-data-pipelines-for-open-ocean/>
- <https://frictionlessdata.io/software/>
- <https://frictionlessdata.io/standards/>